

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXXV. KOSTANECKI ACETYLATION OF METHYL 2:4-DIHYDROXY-5-ACYL- AND -3-ACYL BENZOATES

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Kostanecki acetylation of methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-butyryl-, 5-propionyl-, -3-propionyl- and -3-acetyl- benzoates is described. The chromones have been obtained in each case and identified as such by comparison with the authentic specimens.

A vigorous acylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones by the Kostanecki reaction provides a useful method for the synthesis of chromones containing substituents in different positions. The attempt to utilise the Kostanecki reaction for the synthesis of chromones containing alkyl groups in the benzene nucleus was made by Wittig *et al.* (*Annalen*, 1926, 466, 178), who acetylated different substituted phenols. Desai and Hamid (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 287) and Desai and Desai (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 249) have synthesised chromones containing various alkyl groups in the benzene nucleus by the Kostanecki reaction from alkyl resacetophenones.

Shah *et al.* (*this Journal*, 1942, 19, 487) studied the effect of groups like chloro, bromo and nitro in the resorcinol by heating the substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate.

It was thought of interest to synthesise chromones containing CO₂H and CO₂Me groups in the benzene nucleus. For synthesising these chromones methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate was prepared by Friedel and Crafts' method as described by Desai and Radha (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 1A, 46) and methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-propionylbenzoate and its γ -isomer were prepared as described by Trivedi and Sethna (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 245; 1952, 29, 141). We also synthesised methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoate and its γ -isomer by heating methyl 2:4-dihydroxybenzoate in presence of butyric anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride. The isomers were separated by treating the product with cold petroleum ether, and were characterised by preparing their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Sethna and Parkhi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1955, Part III, p. 115) subjected methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate to the Kostanecki reaction and obtained only the diacetoxy derivative, while methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate gave a mixture of chromones. Simultaneously, we were also working on this line, and it was observed by us that the esters with the higher alkyl groups, such as methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-propionylbenzoate, when heated with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, furnished 7-acetoxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone (I: R = COMe; R₁ = CO₂Me; R₂ = Me). Hydrolysis of the above chromone by dilute ammonia afforded 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone (I: R = H; R₁ = CO₂Me; R₂ = Me), while 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (I: R = H; R₁ = COOH; R₂ = Me) was obtained on alkali hydrolysis in the cold. The decarboxylation of the last chromone furnished 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (I: R = R₁ = H; R₂ = Me), which was identified by its m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen prepared by the method of Canter *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1255).

Similarly, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoate furnished 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone (I: R = H; R₁ = CO₂Me; R₂ = Me). By alkali hydrolysis of the above chromone in the cold 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone (I: R = H; R₁ = COOH; R₂ = Et) was obtained, which on decarboxylation afforded 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone

(I: $R=R_1=H$; $R_2=Et$). It was identified by its m.p. and mixed m.p. with the specimen prepared by the method of Canter *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The Kostanecki reaction of methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-propionylbenzoate furnished a mixture of three chromones: (a) 5-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone (II: $R_1=CO_2Me$; $R_2=Me$), (b) 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (II: $R_1=COOH$; $R_2=Me$), and (c) 5-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (II: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$). The chromones were separated as described in the Experimental. The chromone (a) on alkaline hydrolysis gave the chromone (b), which on decarboxylation furnished the chromone (c). It was identified as such by its m.p. and mixed m.p. with the specimen prepared by the method of Limaye and Kelkar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 241). Similarly, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate on the Kostanecki reaction furnished a mixture of three chromones: (d) 5-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone (II: $R_1=CO_2Me$; $R_2=COMe$), (e) 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone (II: $R_1=COOH$; $R_2=COMe$), and (f) 5-hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone (II: $R_1=H$; $R_2=COMe$). These were separated as described in the Experimental. The chromone (d) on alkaline hydrolysis in the cold furnished the chromone (e) which on decarboxylation and subsequent deacetylation afforded 5-hydroxy-2-methylchromone. The same chromone was obtained on decarboxylation and deacetylation of the chromone (e). These were identified by comparing with the specimen prepared by the method as described by Limaye and Kelkar (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoate and Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate

To a solution of methyl 2:4-dihydroxybenzoate (8.4 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (13.6 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) was added. Butyric anhydride (7.5 g.) was slowly added to the above mixture, and after heating in a water bath for 4 hours it was poured on ice-cold HCl (dil.). Nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation, which was continued further to obtain the steam volatile product (2.2 g.).

The solid was treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-80°, 30 c.c.) in cold, and filtered. The insoluble residue was crystallised from dilute ethanol in white needles, m.p. 90° (1.8 g.). It was found to be methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoate (β -isomer). (Found: C, 60.6; H, 5.84. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.88%).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the keto-ester, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from ethanol in microcrystals, m.p. 283°. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.4%).

2:4-Dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the keto-ester with 10% NaOH solution. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in tiny plates, m.p. 199°. (Found: C, 59.0; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 58.9; H, 5.4%).

The decarboxylation of the keto-ester afforded 4-butyrylresorcinol, m.p. 69°, undepressed by admixture with the authentic sample.

The petroleum ether extract on evaporation furnished a solid which crystallised from ethanol in white, woolly needles, m.p. 69° (0.5 g.), depressed to 52° by admixture with the β -isomer. It was methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate. (Found: C, 60.3; H, 5.85. $C_{12}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.88%).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of the keto-ester (γ -isomer) crystallised from ethanol in tiny plates, m.p. 270°. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.4%).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid was obtained by hydrolysis of the keto-ester by 10% NaOH solution. It was crystallised from ethanol in small plates, m.p. 182°. (Found: C, 58.8; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 58.9; H, 5.4%).

The decarboxylation of the same ester afforded 2-butyrylresorcinol, m.p. 115°, undepressed by admixture with the authentic specimen.

Kostanecki Acetylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-5-propionylbenzoate

To the mixture of anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g.) and the keto-ester (1.0 g.) acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) and 4-5 drops of pyridine were added. The mixture, after heating in an oil bath at 140-50° for 16 hours, was poured in water. The solid was first treated with 5% $NaHCO_3$ solution, followed by 5% NaOH solution, to remove acidic products. The residue was crystallised from methanol in shining yellow needles, m.p. 126°. It gave no colour reaction with ferric chloride. It was found to be 7-acetoxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone. (Found: C, 62.00; H, 4.84. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.10; H, 4.83%).

7-Hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone was obtained by treating the above acetoxy-chromone (0.5 g.) with dilute ammonia for 2 hours, and acidifying the solution. The solid crystallised from dilute ethanol in shining plates, m.p. 208°. It dissolves completely in 5% NaOH solution and develops a red colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 4.76. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 60.5; H, 4.65%).

7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone was obtained by keeping overnight the above hydroxychromone in 5% NaOH solution, and acidifying the alkaline solution. It was crystallised from ethanol in brown needles, m.p. 294°. It dissolves with effervescence of carbon dioxide in 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and forms a reddish colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 5.11; $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 69.46; H, 5.14%).

Hydrolysis of this chromone with 10% NaOH solution afforded 2:4-dihydroxy-5-propionylbenzoic acid, m.p. 260°, and decarboxylation of the same chromone yielded 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone, m.p. 262°. The mixed m.p. with the authentic specimens remained undepressed.

Kostanecki Acetylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoate

A mixture of 5-butyryl keto-ester (1.0 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.), fused sodium acetate (2.0 g.) and 4-5 drops of pyridine was heated at 140-50° for 16 hours. The product on purification crystallised from ethanol in lustrous rhombic plates, m.p. 138°. It is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution but soluble in 5% NaOH solution. It develops a red colour with ferric chloride solution. It was found to be 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone. (Found: C, 64.25; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.4%).

7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone was obtained from the above chromone by keeping it in 5% NaOH solution, and acidifying it. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in brown

needles, m.p. 284°. It dissolves with effervescence in 5% NaHCO₃ solution and develops a red colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 63.0; H, 4.9. C₁₃H₁₂O₆ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.84%).

Hydrolysis of the carboxychromone with 10% NaOH solution afforded 2:4-dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoic acid, which crystallised from dilute ethanol in tiny needles, m.p. 199°, while decarboxylation of the same chromone furnished a solid which was crystallised from ethanol in prismatic needles, m.p. 238°. It was shown to be 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-2-methylchromone by its mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen.

Kostanecki Acetylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate

Acetylation was carried out under usual conditions. The crude product was dissolved in 5% NaHCO₃ solution, and filtered. The alkaline solution on acidification afforded a solid which was crystallised from dilute ethanol in tiny needles, m.p. 247°. It is also soluble in 5% NaOH and sodium carbonate solutions, and develops a red colour with ferric chloride. It was found to be 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 3.9. C₁₃H₁₀O₆ requires C, 59.4; H, 3.82%).

The residue, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, was treated with 5% Na₂CO₃ solution in cold for 4 hours, and filtered. The clear solution on acidification gave a solid which was crystallised from dilute ethanol in yellowish microcrystals, m.p. 143°. It shows a red colour with ferric chloride solution and a brown colour in H₂SO₄ (conc.). It was 5-hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone. (Found: C, 59.9; H, 4.5. C₁₂H₁₀O₄ requires C, 60.1; H, 4.6%).

The residue, insoluble in sodium carbonate solution, was crystallised from ethanol in brown microcrystals, m.p. 122°. It is completely soluble in 5% NaOH solution and shows a red colour with ferric chloride solution. It was found to be 5-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone. (Found: C, 60.7; H, 3.52. C₁₄H₁₂O₆ requires C, 60.9; H, 4.45%).

Hydrolysis of the above chromone with 5% NaOH solution afforded 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone, crystallised from ethanol in small needles, m.p. 242°; while hydrolysis with 10% NaOH gave 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic acid, m.p. 199°. Decarboxylation of the same chromone furnished 5-hydroxy-3-acetyl-2-methylchromone which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 143°. The mixed m.p. of these products with authentic specimens remained undepressed.

Kostanecki Acetylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-propionylbenzoate

The reaction was carried out under usual conditions. The product after removal of unchanged components was kept overnight in 5% NaHCO₃ solution, and then filtered. The solution on acidification furnished a solid which was crystallised from ethanol in small plates, m.p. 240°. It develops a red colour with ferric chloride. It was found to be 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone. (Found: C, 61.12; H, 4.22. C₁₂H₁₀O₆ requires C, 61.58; H, 4.27%).

The residue, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, was treated with 5% Na₂CO₃ solution, in cold, and then filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a solid which was crystallised from dilute ethanol in tiny plates, m.p. 154°. It is soluble in 5% NaOH solution and in H₂SO₄ (conc.); it produces a red colour with ferric chloride. It was 5-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone.

The residue, insoluble also in sodium carbonate solution, was found to be 5-hydroxy-6-methoxycarbonyl-2:3-dimethylchromone, m.p. 136°. It is easily soluble in NaOH solution and develops a yellow colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.). (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.7. C₁₃H₁₂O₆ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8%).

Hydrolysis of the above chromone with 5% NaOH solution yielded 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone which crystallised from ethanol in small needles, m.p. 240°. It dissolves with effervescence in sodium bicarbonate solution, and exhibits a red colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 61.62; H, 4.3. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 61.55; H, 4.2%).

Hydrolysis of the same chromone with 10% NaOH solution gave 2:4-dihydroxy-3-propionylbenzoic acid, m.p. 182°. The same acid was also obtained by the vigorous hydrolysis of 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2:3-dimethylchromone.

Authors' thanks are due to the Ahmedabad Education Society for providing facilities.

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Received April 6, 1960.